

OUT OF POCKET PAYMENT SCENARIO OF PATIENTS IN MEDICINE AND SURGERY WARD, CMCH- "A BURDEN ON POOR?"

Samira Hayee¹ Jahan E nur¹ Ainul Hasan¹ Sabbir Ahmed¹ Imtiaz Uddin¹

ABSTRACT

Background In Bangladesh the financing of healthcare mainly comes from 3 sources i.e. Government or public exchequer, out of pocket payment (OOP) by the users and foreign aid by the development partners. Like many low and middle income countries OOP payment constitute a major portion of payment strategy for healthcare in Bangladesh. Large and unpredictable health costs can expose to substantial financial risk and at most extreme levels can result in poverty. So identifying the components associated with healthcare expenses should prove meaningful to future policy formulation in Bangladesh.

Objectives The primary aim was to assess the OOP payment of patients in a single admission in medicine and surgery department of Chittagong Medical College Hospital (CMCH), the comparison of medical and non-medical aspects of this cost, the affordability of patients and its impact on their socio economic conditions.

Methods A descriptive type of cross sectional study was conducted on 83 respondents in medicine and surgery in-patient departments of Chittagong Medical College Hospital (CMCH) and the OOP payments during a single hospital admission in medical and non-medical sectors were compared.

Results In this study, we found that medical expenses are more than the non-medical expenses. Due to insufficient government support for doing routine investigations, transportation and cost of bearings, tips costs to non-paid staff the OOP has been increased. Among 83 respondents, 60% and 70.33% people having monthly income of <5000tk and 10000-20000tk respectively had to take loans to meet up this burden over them. Furthermore, majority (87%) are facing financial crisis due to their OOP payment.

Conclusion Our study gives an insight about different sectors of OOP payments by the patients during a single hospital admission. This study focuses on the urgency of developing new strategies and alternative financing mechanism for healthcare system in Bangladesh.

Key words: OOP, THE, per capita, GDP, USD, BDT, Bangladesh, CMCH

INTRODUCTION

Bangladesh has a per-capita health expenditure of US\$ 37 which is one-third of the World Health Organization (WHO)-recommended \$85-112. Experts suggested increasing the health spending at an adequate level for receiving sufficient and quality healthcare which can ensure universal health coverage (UHC). As per-capita health spending is less in Bangladesh, out-of-pocket (OOP) expense is one of the highest in South East Asia with the lowest government share putting UHC under great threat¹. It is clear that Bangladesh spends too little resources (as a percentage of its GDP) on health care. It is important to note that the health expenditure (THE) as a percentage of the GDP increased only marginally between 2007 and 2012 – from 3.3% to 3.5% of the GDP, an increase of less than 1% in a decade.²

1. Intern Doctor, Chittagong Medical College Hospital
2. 5th year MBBS, Chittagong Medical College

According to 2012 Bangladesh National Health Accounts, the per capita health expenditure was the highest in Dhaka Division. While Dhaka consumed more than 41% of the THE, the share of Barisal and Sylhet districts in the Total Health Expenditure were only 4.9% and 4.35% respectively.²

Out of pocket payments on healthcare forms a major barrier to health seeking behavior. The poor having no financial protection are more prone to suffer as a consequence of the disease. Out of pocket payment is defined as, "Direct payments made by individuals to healthcare providers at the time of service use, these exclude any pre payments such as tax insurance or other contributions."³ The OOP share of total health expenditure has increased from 55.9% in 1997 to 59.9% in 2005 to 63.3% in 2012 according to the latest national health accounts survey.⁴ Furthermore, Mahmud showed, the urban patients had more spent money for healthcare (US \$ 38.29) than the patients of rural 11(US\$ 21.21).- The cost of medicines (US \$16.98) was the highest cost driver (61.38% of 12 total OOP health expenditure) followed by physician fee (US \$ 3.70).⁵ However, there are enormous disparities in out-of-pocket spending by income level. Individuals in the richest quintile spend 7 times more overall than those in the poorest quintile, and 6 times as much in the case of medicines in 2010.⁶

OOP payments for health can cause households to incur catastrophic expenditure. Reliance on out-of-pocket expenditure for health services leads to a catastrophic burden for many households in Asia including Bangladesh. Rahman found by analyzing urban people from a metropolitan city of Bangladesh that 9% of households face financial catastrophe due to health spending and such catastrophe is four times higher in poorest households than the richest ones.⁷ Because public spending is much lower, people have to pay for health from their own pocket (OPP) which is about two-third (64.7%) in 2016 .The Global standard for out of pocket payment (OPP) is less than 32 percent.⁸ Furthermore, 3.5% of total population fell into poverty annually due to OOP spending for healthcare, which corresponds to economic impoverishment of 5 million people in Bangladesh.⁹ In spite of getting admitted in a government hospital, a patient has to bear quite a large amount of money after each hospital admission. Previous studies lack specific information about average money spent in each hospital stay and detailed information on different sectors of non medical costs. Thus the purpose of this study was to assess the average cost of patient in a single admission in medicine and surgery wards and different aspects of medical and non-medical costs. Moreover, there was an overview of various sources to meet up this expenses and financial burden faced by the respondents.

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive type of cross sectional study was conducted to assess the out of pocket payments by patients in a single admission in Chittagong Medical College and Hospital Bangladesh. Data were obtained from a single setting in Medicine and surgery inpatient departments having 400 and 200 beds respectively on 2nd November 2018 from 9 a.m. to 4 p.m. Over 600 population, 83 respondents were selected by simple random sampling. Here P value was <0.05 and margin of error was 10%. We have selected those patients who have been admitted in the Medicine and surgery in-patient departments of CMCH for more than 4 days and who were present there during data collection period. Data were collected by face to face interviews with the patients, their caregivers and from bills receipts collected from them using a prepared pretested and mixed type of questionnaire. The calculation of OOP payments included medical and non- medical costs. Medical costs comprise of drugs and investigation costs in a single hospital stay whereas non-medical costs included transport, food, outside agents, tips to non-paid staff and bearing costs.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

Informed consent were sought from every respondent before enrollment. Written consent were taken from the illiterate ones.

RESULTS

A total sample of 83 respondents with a single hospital stay in medicine and surgery in patient departments for >4 days were selected for study. Among them, 59(71%) were male and 24 (29%) were female. (Table 1), whereas highest frequency (20.5%) was seen in 4150 years of age group. About half (51.8%) of the studied individuals were illiterate. Among the 33 literates, 18(21.6%) completed up to primary education, 11(13.25%) studied up to class 8 and 2(2.4%) were graduates. 36.14% (30) of the subjects had a monthly income of about BDT 10000-20000.25.3% (21), 1.2% (1) had BDT 20000-30000 and BDT >50000 respectively. The mean total of OOP in single admission of more than 4 days was 22768.15 taka (BDT) of which 79.55% was medical expenses and 20.45% was non-medical expenses.

Figure 1: Distribution of total cost

Table 1: Socio-demographic profile of the study population (n= 83)

Variables		Frequency	Percent(%)
Sex	Male	59	71%
	Female	24	29%
Age			
	11-20	10	12%
	21-30	13	15%
	31-40	14	17%
	41-50	17	20%
	51-60	14	18%
	61-70	11	13%
	71-80	4	5%
Educational Status			
	Illiterate	43	51.8%
	Literate	40	48.2%
Residence			
	Metropolitan	26	31%
	Non Metropolitan	57	69%
Occupation			
	Businessman	5	6%
	Small Businessman	8	10%
	Farmer	14	17%
	Housewife	16	19%
	Industrial Worker	6	7%
	Service Holder	8	10%
	Driver	3	3%
	Day Laborer	3	3%
	Garment Worker	7	9%
	Others	14	16%
Monthly Income			
	<5000	9	11%
	5000-10000	21	25%
	10000-20000	30	36%
	20000-30000	18	22%
	30000-40000	1	1%
	40000-50000	3	4%
	>50000	1	1%
Earning Members			
	1 Member	50	60%
	2 Member	22	27%
	3 Member	8	9%
	>3 member	3	4%

Patients living outside metropolitan city had higher mean total cost (BDT 22606.94) than the patients of Chittagong metropolitan city (BDT 21,530). The cost of investigations was the highest cost driver (38.58%) of the total OOP expenses, followed by drugs cost (37.58%). Amongst the non-medical costs, 9.35% was the food expenses for the caregivers. 2.21% and 2.75% of the total cost were spent to pay the outside

agents & tips of non-paid staff which ultimately increased their cost burden. (Table 2). 67.46% (56) of the respondents got treatment from outside before admitting to CMCH. Among them who received outside hospital treatment, only 12.5% (7) could bear their expenditure from monthly income but 41 (23%) had to take loans to bear the expenses.

Table 2: Different sectors of expenses in medicine and surgery ward patients (n=83)

Cost Sector	Mean	Median	Percentile			% of total cost
			25	50	75	
Drugs	8558.33	5000	2500	5000	8000	37.58%
Investigation	8818.59	7000	3675	7000	9625	38.73%
Transport	1803.85	1000	500	1000	2925	7.92%
Tips for non-paid staff	623.86	250	100	2500	600	2.75%
Food	2129.38	1650	800	1650	2500	9.35%
Outside Agents	491.07	300	200	300	500	2.21%
Bearings	171.69	200	100	200	250	0.75%
Total	22768.15	18000	12400	18000	29500	100%

Figure 2: Distribution of respondents according to the place of investigation

However, patients admitting directly in CMCH, 25.9% could bear their total expenses solely from their monthly income and 29.6% took additional loans.

Majority of the respondents bought their prescribed drugs despite having financial problems. (Table -3)

Table 3: Different sources of meeting up expenses with respect to patient's h/o outside treatment

Source Of meeting Expenditure	H/O Previous Treatment before coming to CMCH		Completion of Drug buying	Completion of Investigation
	Yes	No		
Monthly Income	12.5%(7)	25.9%(7)	96.02%	81.8%
Monthly Income, Loan	41%(23)	29.6%(8)	88.6%	94.3%
Monthly Income, Loan, Donation	4.8%(3)	3.7%(1)	100%	100%
Monthly Income, Savings	3.6%(2)	3.7%(1)	100%	100%
Monthly Income, Donation	1.8%(1)	3.7%(1)	100%	100%
Monthly Income, Selling Asset	12.5%(7)	7.4%(2)	100%	84.3%
Loan	12.5%(7)	18.5%(5)	100%	91.8%
Loan, Donation	5.4%(3)	3.7%(1)	100%	87.8%
Donation, Selling Asset	3.6%(2)	0%(0)	100%	100%
Donation	1.8%(1)	3.7%(1)	100%	0%

Figure 3: Financial Crisis faced by the respondents

94.3% patients were able to do all the advised investigations who took extra loans along with their monthly income whereas 18.2% did not do all the investigations who could not take any loans or had no savings. On average, 94.6% (53) of the respondents (n=57) who had history of outside treatment were able to buy all the prescribed drugs and 91.1% (51) could do all the required investigations. 42.20% (35) of the patients went to the private diagnostic centres, 24.10% (20) to CMCH for their investigations. 31 (37.34%)

had to take loans along with their monthly income to meet up their OOP payments in a single admission. (Table -4) Respondents with <5000 and 5000-10000 BDT monthly income had a mean total cost of BDT 16763 and BDT 20039.05 respectively which was almost three fold. 100% Subjects having monthly income BDT >30000 could pay their total OOP

expenses in a single hospital stay solely by their monthly income (Table 5). 87.95% (73) of the study population faced financial crisis due to this disproportionate OOP expenditure in each hospital admission (fig 3). Despite this financial burden, among the 83 respondents 77.1% were satisfied with the treatment in CMCH

Table 4: Different sources of meeting up OOP

Sources of OOP payment	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Monthly Income	14	16.86746988
Monthly Income, Loan	31	37.34939759
Monthly Income, Loan, Donation	4	4.819277108
Monthly Income, Savings	3	3.614457831
Monthly Income, Donations	2	2.409638554
Monthly Income, Selling Asset	9	10.84337349
Loan	12	14.45783133
Loan, Donation	4	4.819277108
Donation, Selling Asset	2	2.409638554
Donation	2	2.409638554
Total	83	100%

Table 5: Sources of paying OOP expenses in different socio-economical levels (multiple)

Monthly Income	Total Cost (BDT)	Source Of paying OOP expenses	Respondents	Percentage (%)
<5000	16,763	Monthly Income	8	80
		Loan	6	60
		Donation	2	20
		Selling Asset	1	10
5000-10000	20039.05	Monthly Income	15	71.42
		Loan	13	61.9
		Selling Asset	5	23.8
		Donation	3	14.28
		savings	1	4.76
10000-20000	18768.33	Loan	22	73.33
		Monthly Income	19	63.33
		Donation	2	6.66
		savings	1	3.33
		Selling Asset	1	3.33
20000-30000	34,191.11	Monthly Income	18	100
		Loan	11	61.11
		Selling Asset	3	16.66
		savings	2	11.11
		Donation	1	5.55
30000-40000	18000	Monthly Income	1	100
40000-50000	21,133	Monthly Income	3	100
		Loan	1	33.33

DISCUSSION

The government of any country has a prime responsibility about the development of health facilities as well as medical system which should be applied through allocating a significant percentage. Of total expenditures in health sector. Unfortunately, the yearly allocation in Bangladesh is far short of required level set by World Health Organization (WHO) which is at least 15% of total budget of a country.¹⁰ Another study has shown, Bangladesh's per capita health expenditure is \$32 in 2016, which is the lowest in the region compared to India (61 USD), Afghanistan (55 USD), Nepal (39 USD), Bhutan (90 USD), Pakistan and Sri Lanka (102 USD).

In the last few decades Bangladesh has achieved commendable progress in health and socio-economic development. Despite these achievements, the health sector faces multiple challenges in ensuring universal healthcare among which increasing trend of out pocket expenses is a significant one. This study has identified the major factors attributing to this unreasonable increase in out of pocket payments for patients in CMCH. A range of factors including socio economic status, demographic characteristics, place of residence, history of previous treatment outside are associated with higher OOP costs. Our study showed that the sex of individuals was significantly related with OOP as the total average cost of OOP payment was higher in male than female. Previous studies have shown that OOP health expenditure was more significantly associated with the urban communities.^{5,12} But in our study we found that, average total OOP payment is more for the people who live outside the metropolitan city than the people living inside the city. This is mostly due to the use of microbus, taxi and other transports to come to the tertiary care hospital, CMCH. More over the patients' caregiver have to travel frequently from hospitals to home. Consequently, the total costs increase. Study suggests that, medicine OOP spending has dominated total OOP payments over the years. Hence, it can be suggested that expenditure on medicines is major cause of catastrophe and impoverishment at the household level.¹³

Another research in India has shown that, medicines purchase alone constituted over 70% of overall OOP payments.¹⁴ On the contrary, our study reported that, Investigation expenses are the major cost drivers in OOP in the admitted patients in CMCH. This might be due to the supply of some cost free medications by the government in CMCH as well as the tendency of doing diagnostic tests in private facilities. We also

found that, a large percentage of studied population (42.02%) did the diagnostic tests in different diagnostic centers. Apart from medical cost, some non-medical factors play a significant role to increase the OOP payment in hospitalized patients. These include, transportation costs, food costs of the care, bearing costs, tips to non-paid staff and outside agent. This is consistent with previous findings.¹⁵

Our study demonstrates that, the burden of OOP due to single hospital stay was higher in lower earning groups which also supports previous research findings.^{5, 16} Respondents with monthly income BDT <30,000 had to incur high OOP expenses which was about two to three folds of their income. It may be argued that when the OOP payment is large as a share of household budgets, households are at risk of sacrificing current consumption of the necessities of life to pay for these costs.¹⁷ We also found that, to meet up this disproportionate amount of money, majority of the patients had to depend on taking loans, donations and selling assets which corresponds with another research in INDIA.¹⁸ Every year, about 150 million people face financial catastrophe, due to OOP cost directly which is similar to our findings.¹⁹ A study in Vietnam recorded 38% of households in 1993 that had incurred catastrophic payment at the 5% threshold level. A study in Nigeria revealed that as many as 39% of households recorded OOP health-care payments in excess of 5% of their total household income.^{21,22} In our study, it was revealed that the major portion of the studied population had to face financial crisis due to taking loans, selling assets, taking donations. Our study proves that, despite this unreasonable expenses in each hospitalization carried out by the patients, most of them could afford all the drugs all and almost all the investigations advised by their physicians. There is a strong association of mean total cost by the patients with history of outside treatment. Those who received outside treatment before coming to CMCH tend to take more loans, donations, sell properties to meet up the total cost. This may be due to higher OOP payments in private treatment facilities. In spite of having huge financial burden, majority of the respondents stated that, they were satisfied with the treatment provided by CMCH.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that the majority of the OOP payments comprise of costs incurring for laboratory investigations and drugs. In addition to this non-medical costs like food, transport, bearings, tips to non-paid staff, outside agent costs have turned the total expenses into a huge burden to our respondents

during a single hospital stay. Our study identifies the place of residence, family wealth, history of getting previous treatment outside and investigations done in private laboratories as significant factors influencing out of pocket payments in CMCH. This also highlights upon the fact that the less the monthly income the more the financial crisis people are facing. However, a significant number of people meet this inordinate expenses by taking loans and donations. Despite facing all these crisis majority of the people were able to buy all the drugs and do most of investigations advised by the doctors in a single hospital stay. Thus by showing where OOP payments are highest this research might pave the way for the policy makers to identify which section of population is more exposed to disproportionate OOP payments and prone to push themselves below poverty line. Therefore, it might help to explore expanded health financing options.

LIMITATIONS

The limitation of this study is that only the expenses made directly by the patients in a single hospital admission were assessed. Data about the health expenditure allocated for a patient by the government for CMCH could not be obtained. The study also faced some selection bias like many other cross sectional study as some patients did not give consent for interview. Moreover, there was difficulty in collecting information about the detailed lists of expenses, such as cost of public transport or taxi fare or cost of foods like snacks and fruits. This was due to the fact

that the patients did not keep the receipt for these kind of expenditures. So recall bias may be present due to troubles in recalling this information. Furthermore, due to short study period we could not cover a larger sample size. Regardless of the limitations, this study might prove supportive as it focuses on the additional non-medical costs along with the medical ones in different socio economic levels and the impacts over them.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Further research is needed to explore the relation of OOP with the chronicity of disease as well as the pricing mechanism of essential drugs and investigations in government hospitals. Besides this, more studies comparing OOP between government and private hospital can help to know more about the present OOP payment scenario of Bangladesh. To support the government's goal of universal healthcare coverage by 2032, Bangladesh must give priority to health and allocate a much greater proportion of its budget for health care. Accordingly, health loan without interests need to be introduced. Unnecessary non-medical costs like tips to non-paid staff and outside agents should be minimized by ensuring strict rules and regulations. More financial support by the government for laboratory investigations in a public hospital should be provided.

COMPETING INTERESTS

All authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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